

Yeast as a Model for Assessing the Toxicity of Azoxystrobin and Indoxacarb at Different Concentrations and Understanding the Role of Yeast Fermentation against Pesticides

Nahid Sandikly^{1,2,*}, Salem Hayar^{2,3}, and Maurice Millet¹

¹Université de Strasbourg, Institut de Chimie et Procédés pour l'Énergie, l'Environnement et la Santé (ICPEES), CNRS UMR 7515, Groupe de Physico-Chimie de l'Atmosphère, Strasbourg, 1 rue Blessig, 67084 Strasbourg Cedex, France mmillet@unistra.fr

²Lebanese University, Doctoral School of Science and Technology, Platform for Research and Analysis in Environmental Science (EDST-PRASE), Rafik Hariri Campus, Mount Lebanon, Hadath-Baabda 1003, Lebanon sandikly.nahid@gmail.com

³Lebanese University, Department of Plant Protection, Faculty of Agricultural Engineering, Dekwaneh-Matn 90775, Lebanon salem.hayar@ul.edu.lb

*Correspondence: sandikly.nahid@gmail.com

Abstract: This research aimed to analyze the effects of the widely used fungicide strobilurin and the recently developed insecticide oxadiazine on the alcoholic fermentation (AF) carried out by the oenological commercial *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* yeast strain X16. The impact of different concentrations ($\frac{1}{2}$ MRL, MRL, and 2MRL) of both pesticides was evaluated on synthetic wine quality, including yeast cell growth, oenological parameters, color, and pesticide residues. At the highest pesticide concentrations, significant reductions in biomass and tartaric acid ($\text{g}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$) production were observed. However, yeast viability, sugar catabolism, CO_2 production, and synthetic wine color were unaffected by the presence of pesticides. During AF, approximately 30% of azoxystrobin and 78% of indoxacarb residues were dissipated, with indoxacarb dissipation accelerating at higher concentrations, while azoxystrobin dissipation slowed as its concentration increased. Both pesticides had processing factors (PFs) below one by the end of the AF. These results suggest that indoxacarb is rapidly eliminated by yeast cells, whereas azoxystrobin is more gradually dissipated. The fact that there were insignificant differences in the parameters examined implies that the presence of pesticides had no impact on the wine's quality or the AF process.

Keywords: Food analysis; Strobilurin; Azoxystrobin; Oxadiazine; Indoxacarb; *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (X16); Alcoholic Fermentation; Dissipation kinetics; Wine.

1. Introduction

Saccharomyces cerevisiae, an important microorganism, plays a major role in alcoholic fermentation, which ferments a variety of sugars into ethanol, achieving high yields and productivities (Terpou *et al.*, 2019). The presence of undesirable substances as pesticide residues on grapes indirectly affects human health by interfering with natural resources and the food chain (Saied *et al.*, 2021), posing a significant challenge to wine production (Song *et al.*, 2022). These residues can disrupt the fermentation capability of microorganisms, including yeasts and bacteria (Pereira *et al.*, 2021). Residual pesticides have a deleterious impact on wine characteristics like color, aromatic, and phenolic profiles (Noguerol-Pato *et al.*, 2014; Briz-Cid, 2018; Sieiro-Sampedro *et al.*, 2019).

Azoxystrobin [methyl (E)-2-{2-[6-(2-cyanophenoxy) pirimi-din-4-yloxy] phenyl}-3-methoxyacrylate], known as β -methoxyacrylates, is a systemic strobilurin used as the initial treatment during major pathogenic attack (Mpofu

et al., 2021). It was the subject of few studies examining its impact on alcoholic fermentation; it is known to inhibit the growth of yeasts and delay wine fermentation (Cabras *et al.*, 1999) while other proves its non-toxic influence on *S. cerevisiae* fermentation (Regueiro *et al.*, 2015). The fungicidal effect of azoxystrobin is based on the inhibition of mitochondrial respiration through inhibition of the electron transferring Q₀ site in cytochrome b, which is a component of the cytochrome bc₁ complex, also known as Complex III, and located in the inner mitochondrial membrane of fungi (De Melo Abreu *et al.*, 2005). It prevents fungi from producing and germinating spores, and growing mycelium. It is effective against a variety of fungal pathogens at low levels (Gajbhiye *et al.*, 2011).

While (Oliva *et al.*, 2020) demonstrated that indoxacarb has no effect on *S. cerevisiae* indigenous microflora. Indoxacarb (methyl (S)-N-[7-chloro-2,3,4a,5 tetrahydro-4a-(methoxycarbonyl) indeno [1,2-e][1,3,4] oxadiazin-2-ylcarbonyl]-4'(trifluoromethoxy)carbanilate) is a new contact oxadiazine-type insecticide with high insecticidal activity against *Planococcus spp.* and *Lobesia botrana* in viticulture (Angioni *et al.*, 2011). Indoxacarb is a neurotoxic insecticide with a novel mode of action, resulting in the blockage of voltage-dependent sodium channels, leading to the paralysis and death of the targeted species along with its active metabolite DCJW (Oxborough *et al.*, 2015).

However, the wine-making process and other oenological procedures help to reduce the undesirable residues in the finished products (Cabras & Angioni, 2000; Jiménez *et al.*, 2007; Navarro *et al.*, 1999; Oliva *et al.*, 2007; Sala *et al.*, 1996). Winemaking is a typical example of evaluating pesticide transfer processes (Gava *et al.*, 2021). Residues are typically reduced as a result of the numerous technological sub-processes used to make wine, such as pressing, fermenting, fining, and filtration (Cabras & Angioni, 2000; Čuš *et al.*, 2010; Doulia *et al.*, 2016, 2017). According to studies, azoxystrobin on grapes reportedly dissipated slowly during field trials ($t_{1/2} = 15.2$ days) (Cabras *et al.*, 1998). It is well known that it is more persistent in aerobic than anaerobic conditions (Gajbhiye *et al.*, 2011).

Limited research exists on the impact of azoxystrobin and indoxacarb on the oenological commercial *S. cerevisiae* strain X16. The purpose of the current study was to: (1) determine the effect of different concentrations of azoxystrobin and indoxacarb on yeast growth and fermentation properties by studying the changes in viability (%CFU.ml⁻¹), biomass amount (g.l⁻¹), reducing sugar concentration (g.l⁻¹), tartaric acid concentration (g.l⁻¹), and extrapolating CO₂ release from weight loss measures (%) (2) The chromatic properties of the synthetic wine; and (3) the yeast dissipation kinetics during alcoholic fermentation to assess the processing factor (PF).

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Chemicals and Reagents

Technical grade azoxystrobin and indoxacarb (purities > 98.9%) were purchased from Dr. Ehrenstorfer GmbH, Augsburg, Germany. These pesticides were chosen based on data from a sampling campaign conducted in Lebanese grape cultivation (Sandikly, Hayar and Millet, 2019). **Figure 1** depicts the chemical structures of the pesticides used **Table 1** summarizes their physical and chemical characteristics. For each pesticide, standard stock solutions (1000 mg.l⁻¹) prepared in acetonitrile (ACN, Sigma-Aldrich International GmbH) were used to prepare the individual working solution (10 mg.l⁻¹), and maintained in the dark at -18°C.

Figure 1. Chemical structure diagrams of: (a) azoxystrobin, (b) indoxacarb.

Analytical-grade solvents and reagents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich International GmbH (Munich, Schnellendorf, Germany). Primary secondary amine (PSA), anhydrous magnesium sulfate (MgSO_4), and sodium chloride (NaCl) were supplied by Agilent Technologies (Santa Clara, CA, USA). The active commercial dry yeast powder, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* strain (*S. cerevisiae*-X16) marketed as ZYMAFLORE[®] by LAFFORT l'oenologie par nature, and the pasteurized grape juice samples from the Cabernet variety were awarded by Château Kefraya, a vineyard castle located in the Western Beqaa District in the Republic of Lebanon. The media culture Yeast Extract Peptone Dextrose (YPD/YEPD) was supplied by Merck KGaA Darmstadt, Germany. Ultra-pure water was generated by a MilliQ water purification system (Millipore, Billerica, MA, USA).

Table 1. Physical and chemical characteristics of the four fortified pesticides in synthetic grape juice.

Chemical Group	Molecule	Molecular Formula	Mode of Action	Log K_{ow} ¹	Solubility in Water (g l ⁻¹) at 20°C	Molecular Weight (g mol ⁻¹)
		CAS number	Use			
Strobilurin	Azoxystrobin	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{O}_6$	Systemic	2.50	6.7	403.40
		(131860-33-8)	Fungicide			
Oxadiazine	Indoxacarb	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{ClF}_3\text{N}_3\text{O}_7$	Contact	4.65	0.2	527.83
		(173584-44-6)	Insecticide			

¹Octanol-water partition coefficient

2.2. Preculture conditions for yeast strains

The commercial wine yeast strain X16 was rehydrated in a tenfold volume of sterile water at 37°C for 30 min. The rehydrated yeast cells were then pre-cultured on YPD agar plates (2% glucose, 2% peptone, 1% yeast extract, and 2% agar) at 22°C without agitation for 48 hours. A single yeast colony was subsequently inoculated into 100 mL of YPD broth and incubated at 22°C for 24 hours in a shaking incubator (Multi Stack, shaking: LabTech, Sorisole (BG), Italy) at 150 rpm.min⁻¹ to prepare the yeast strain's starter culture (Scariot, Delamare and Echeverrigaray, 2022).

2.3. Alcoholic fermentation conditions

Pasteurized samples of grape juice with a high sugar content (glucose 200 g.l⁻¹) were used. These samples were fortified with azoxystrobin and indoxacarb at three different concentrations, micro-vinification was performed with addition of 1 x 10⁷ cells.ml⁻¹ of precultured yeast under aseptic conditions, as detailed in **Table 2**. The toxicity of the solvent was evaluated using solely acetonitrile as a solvent, in addition to the control carried out under the same conditions. The fermentation was maintained for 16 days at a controlled pH of 3.4 ± 0.3, temperature of 30 ± 1 °C, and at 150 rpm.min⁻¹. Three replicates of each assay were conducted aseptically. The progress of the fermentation was monitored by extrapolating CO₂ release from weight loss measures throughout the process. Fermentation was assumed to have ended when the weight was steady with values below 0.02 g for three days (Sun *et al.*, 2019).

Table 2. Fortified concentration of pesticides during micro-vinification process.

Molecule	Pasteurized Grape Juice Volume (ml) ¹	Spiked Concentration (mg kg ⁻¹)		
		½MRL	MRL ²	2MRL
Azoxystrobin	100	1.5	3	6
Indoxacarb		1	2	4

¹ Micro-vinification was performed in three replicates; ² Approved EU-MRLs (European Commission (EC), 2022)

2.4. Alcoholic fermentation analysis

For each sample, an aliquot is centrifuged to remove the supernatant, and the pellet (containing the yeast cells) is washed twice in distilled water. The culture absorbance at 660 nm was used to measure cell poliferation (Zhang *et al.*, 2018). The dry yeast cell weight was determined gravimetrically in three replicates by placing the wet biomass at 100 °C for 24 hours. The biomass concentration is then determined by calculating the difference between the filter mass before and after drying on the volume of the sample and represented in (g.l⁻¹) (Sarris *et al.*, 2009; Terpou *et al.*, 2019). To determine cell viability, the methylene blue staining method was used to differentiate the viable and non-viable yeast cells (Bonora and Mares, 1982).

Additionally, the sugar content (g.l⁻¹) of the synthetic wine was determined by the dinitrosalicylic acid method (DNS) during fermentation (Miller, 1959). The total acidity (expressed by g.l⁻¹ of tartaric acid) in samples was assessed by titration with NaOH (0.1 M) to pH = 8.2 (Zhong *et al.*, 2020).

2.5. Chromatic parameters of wine

The color intensity (CI) of the wine was determined by calculating the sum of absorbance at wavelengths of 420, 520, and 620 nm, or A₄₂₀, A₅₂₀, and A₆₂₀. The hue (color tonality) was expressed as the ratio of A₄₂₀ and A₅₂₀. Chromatic characteristics were measured using quartz cells with a 0.1 cm path length, following the method outlined by (Petruzzi *et al.*, 2015).

2.6. Evaluation of the Minimal Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

A micro-dilution approach, as described by (Kosel, Raspor and Čadež, 2019), was used to determine the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of the pesticides on 96-well plates. A serial twofold dilution of the pesticides

was made in YPD broth containing yeast suspension of approximately 1×10^7 cells.mL⁻¹. For the negative controls, wells were filled with 100 μ L of diluted stock solutions of pesticide, whereas for the positive control, just YPD broth was introduced to the working yeast suspension. The plates were incubated for 48 hours at 28°C in the dark and the proliferation of yeast was assessed by measuring the optical density at 660 nm (OD₆₆₀) using a BioTek ELx800 microplate reader. The MIC was determined as the lowest pesticide concentration at which no yeast growth was observed.

2.7. Pesticide extraction and clean-up

Azoxystrobin and indoxacarb were extracted from the wine matrix following the modified QuEChERS cleanup technique (Jiang *et al.*, 2009). The chosen technique was determined by the results of recovery experiments conducted using three alternative techniques (preliminary results). For the extraction, 10 g of supernatant was collected after centrifuging the wine samples for 5 minutes at 4000 rpm and 4°C to separate the yeast cells. The supernatant was then transferred into a 50 mL propylene centrifuge tube. To the supernatant, 5 mL of acetonitrile (ACN) was added, and the mixture was vigorously shaken for 1 minute, followed by the addition of 4g of MgSO₄ and 3 g of NaCl, and the tube was manually shaken for 1 minute. Afterward, the tube was then centrifuged for 8 minutes at 4000 rpm. Then a dispersive-SPE cleanup was done by transferring 1 mL of supernatant to a dispersive solid-phase extraction (d-SPE) minicentrifuge tube containing 150 mg of MgSO₄ and 50 mg of PSA. The tube was shaken for 1 minute, centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 5 min. The obtained supernatant was filtered through a 0.22 μ m PTFE filter, diluted with acetonitrile to fit within the quantitative range of the calibration curve, and then injected directly into UHPLC-MS/MS for analysis.

2.8. Instrumentation and UHPLC-MS/MS analytical conditions

The pesticide analysis in the extracts were performed using Thermo Scientific UltiMate 3000 UHPLC coupled to Thermo Scientific™ Q Exactive™ Hybrid Quadrupole-Orbitrap™ Mass Spectrometer. The instrument was equipped with a C₁₈ Thermo Scientific Accucore aQ column (100 x 2.1mm, 2.6 μ m) and a Guard Column Accucore 10mm. The mobile phase (A): 2% methanol buffered with 0.1% formic acid and 5mM ammonium formate; the mobile phase (B): 2% water in methanol buffered with 0.1% formic acid and 5mM ammonium formate; injection volume 5 μ L; flow rate 0.3 mL min⁻¹; equilibrium time 0.5 min; mobile phase gradients: 100% A to 0% B over 0.5 min, decreased at 30% A and 70% B for 7 min, held at 100% B for 21 min then increased to 100% A to 0% B for 27 min; the column was maintained at 25°C.

Figure 2. Total ion chromatography (TIC), and relative intensity for (a) azoxystrobin and (b) indoxacarb.

2.9. Method Validation

Method validation was implemented according to (Guidance SANTE/12682/2019, 2019). Linearity (R^2), mean recovery (RM%), within-laboratory repeatability ($RSD_r\%$), reproducibility ($RSD_{RW}\%$), and the limit of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) parameters are established in accordance with SANTE guidance. According to EU SANTE (Guidance SANTE/12682/2019, 2019), the acceptance criteria for the method were as follows: the average recovery values of the method were in the range of 70-120% with precision (%RSD) less than 20%, and linearity coefficient R^2 greater than 0.99.

Linearity was performed by preparing standard calibration curves for the two studied molecules by appropriate dilution of the stock solution with seven concentration gradients (0.005, 0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.045, 0.065 and 0.1 mg.kg⁻¹) on the day of analysis. The linear regression of the calibration curves had a regression coefficient R² greater than 0.99. The tested pesticides had limit of detection and quantification (LOD and LOQ) were between 1 and 6 ng.g⁻¹, which were much lower than their EU-MRLs in wine grapes. The RSD_r% and RSD_{rw}% of the recovery results are used to determine the accuracy and precision of the method. The validation method was performed at three fortification levels (50, 100 and 500 ng.g⁻¹), with five replicates prepared on separate days. After fortification, the samples were left at room temperature for 30 minutes so that the pesticide could be evenly integrated into the matrix. Afterwards, QuEChERS was carried out, followed by UHPLC-MS/MS analysis. The recovery means in our study ranged from 97 to 115%, and the RSD% was under 20% for all values **Table 3**.

Table 3. Average of recovery data (RM%), repeatability (RSD_r%), and reproducibility (RSD_{rw}%), quantification limits (LOD and LOQ), and linearity for azoxystrobin and indoxacarb at the three fortification levels (n = 5 at each level) in pasteurized grape juice medium.

Compound	LOD (µg g ⁻¹)	LOQ (µg g ⁻¹)	Level Spiking (0.05 µg g ⁻¹)			Level Spiking (0.1 µg g ⁻¹)			Level Spiking (0.5 µg g ⁻¹)		
			RM	RSD _r (%)	RSD _{rw}	RM	RSD _r (%)	RSD _{rw}	RM	RSD _r (%)	RSD _{rw}
			Azoxystrobin	0.002	0.006	85	13	11	84	8	7
Indoxacarb	0.001	0.004	84	16	15	83	14	12	80	15	11

2.10. Pesticide dissipation decay model

To determine the dissipation rate, regression equations, and half-life (t_{1/2}) of residues in each winemaking process, experimental data were fitted to a mathematical model. R software is used to analyze the data (Majed, Hayar and Zeitoun, 2021):

$$C_t = C_0 \times e^{-kt} \quad (1)$$

Where:

C_t = the residual concentration at time t (days) (mg kg⁻¹)

C₀ = the starting fortified concentration (mg kg⁻¹)

k = dissipation rate of the molecule/slope of the exponential regression curve (day⁻¹)

The following equation was used to determine the time required for pesticide residue to decrease to half its initial concentration:

$$t_{1/2} = \frac{\ln 2}{k} \quad (2)$$

According to Kittleman (Kittelman *et al.*, 2022), the processing factor (PF) can be used to express the change in pesticide residue levels at the end of fermentation. It is calculated from the ratio of the fortified pesticide concentration in the grapes to the residue concentration in the synthetic wine. Pesticide residue levels decreased throughout processing if the PF value below one. The following equation can be used to calculate the PF (Pan, 2018):

$$PF = \frac{\text{Residue level in synthetic wine at the end of fermentation (mg kg}^{-1}\text{)}}{\text{Initial fortified concentration in grapes at the beginning of fermentation (mg kg}^{-1}\text{)}} \quad (3)$$

2.11. Statistical analysis

For the statistical analysis, the data were loaded into Microsoft Office 2022 and R software v4.2.1 for statistical analysis (p -value estimation; significant differences were assigned to values of $p \leq 0.05$). All reported values are the means \pm standard deviation (SD) of three replicates.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Behavior of *S. cerevisiae* during alcoholic fermentation in the presence of Azoxystrobin and Indoxacarb

The *S. cerevisiae* strain X16 is considered a wild-type yeast selected by the wineries as a potential “starter” for guided fermentations in the production of high-quality wines (El Dana, Hayar and Colosio, 2021). To eliminate the influence of naturally occurring saccharomyces and non-saccharomyces yeast during fermentation (Zara, Caboni and Orro, 2011) and solely examine the impact of an oenological commercial yeast strain, grape juice was pasteurized. In a preliminary evaluation, we monitored the growth of yeast cells in the presence of different concentrations of both fortified pesticides. The pesticides had MIC values higher than the Maximum Residue Level (MRL) based on the results of the minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) evaluation.

The yeast was investigated for their sensitivity to acetonitrile, all yeast parameters and fermentation conditions did not significantly differ from the control during alcoholic fermentation ($p > 0.05$) **Table 4**, demonstrates that the solvent employed to dissolve the pesticide has no effect on the characteristics of yeast cell growth.

Table 4. Effect of added solvent (acetonitrile) on yeast fermentation parameters and chromatic characteristics of wine.

Fermentation condition	Yeast Fermentation Parameters (\pm SD) ¹ at T=16							p^2 Value
	Biomass (g l ⁻¹)	Viability (%CFU ml ⁻¹)	Weight Reduction (%)	Residual Sugar (g l ⁻¹)	Tartaric Acid (g l ⁻¹)	Color Tonality	Color Intensity	
Control	8.493 (\pm 0.140)	84.859 (\pm 0.081)	5.534 (\pm 0.459)	19.599 (\pm 0.036)	1.503 (\pm 0.006)	0.748 (\pm 0.081)	5.355 (\pm 0.140)	Insignificant Difference ($p > 0.05$)
Acetonitrile	8.240 (\pm 0.044)	83.928 (\pm 0.362)	4.944 (\pm 0.133)	19.446 (\pm 0.203)	1.495 (\pm 0.005)	0.724 (\pm 0.082)	5.461 (\pm 0.091)	

¹Mean \pm SD Standard Deviation of three replicates; ²Significant level: ($\alpha = 0.05$)

Yeast Viability

Table 5 shows the evolution of viable yeasts (%CFU.ml⁻¹) during the alcoholic fermentation process to evaluate the cellular toxicity exerted by different pesticide concentrations on yeast cells. Both pesticides show similar behavior. The yeast populations had no significant variance in terms of viability in the presence of different concentrations of azoxystrobin and indoxacarb ($p > 0.05$). Yeast cells respond to pesticide levels in a range of ways, from adaptation to eventual cell death by apoptosis or necrosis (Salgueiro, Sá-Correia and Novais, 1988). Similar adaptive responses of *S. cerevisiae* during fermentation have been described in the literature by (Jawich *et al.*, 2006) to the presence of 2MRL of the triazole fungicide penconazole. In contrast, (Scariot *et al.*, 2018) proved that low concentrations of the quinone fungicide dithianon, having a mode of action similar to that of azoxystrobin (which inhibits yeast’s respiratory metabolism), cause a cytotoxic effect (high mortality) on *S. cerevisiae*, explained by non-apoptotic cell death.

Table 5. The Effect of azoxystrobin and indoxacarb on culture viability of *S. cerevisiae* under fermentation conditions; untreated control, ½MRL, MRL, and 2MRL pesticide enriched.

Viability (%CFU ml ⁻¹) (±SD) ¹	Control	Azoxystrobin			Indoxacarb			p ² Value
		½MRL	MRL	2MRL	½MRL	MRL	2MRL	
	84.86 (±0.08)	85.84 (±0.58)	81.79 (±1.12)	80.76 (±0.89)	86.05 (±1.10)	84.98 (±0.34)	80.19 (±1.11)	Insignificant Difference (p > 0.05)

¹Mean ± SD Standard Deviation of three replicates; ² Significant level: ($\alpha = 0.05$)

Biomass Production

Regarding biomass production (g.l⁻¹) of yeast in the presence of both pesticides **Table 6**, yeast cells exhibited the typical growth pattern of microorganisms produced in the culture broth, including typical latency period growth due to pre-culture, an exponential phase, a stationary phase, and a decline or death phase (Hayek *et al.*, 2020). However, a clear dose-effect negative response of the yeast cells' biomass to the presence of both pesticides is present during alcoholic fermentation.

Table 6. The effect of different concentration of the spiked two molecules on the biomass concentration of *S. cerevisiae* under fermentation conditions.

Molecule	Concentration of Spiked Pesticide (mg kg ⁻¹)	Biomass Concentration (g l ⁻¹) (±SD) ¹						
		T0	T1	T2	T6	T9	T14	T16
Control	0	1.183 (±0.051)	5.203 (±0.013)	9.762 (±0.080)	9.562 (±0.050)	9.297 (±0.038)	9.235 (±0.023)	8.498 (±0.014)
Azoxystrobin	1.5	1.460* (±0.020)	5.883* (±0.086)	9.913 (±0.090)	9.760* (±0.070)	9.497* (±0.104)	9.460* (±0.089)	8.850* (±0.036)
	3	1.320* (±0.026)	5.980* (±0.171)	9.870 (±0.072)	9.223 (±0.189)	9.037 (±0.118)	8.897 (±0.145)	8.197 (±0.031)
	6	1.510* (±0.036)	5.487* (±0.101)	8.603* (±0.061)	8.263* (±0.067)	8.007* (±0.055)	7.950* (±0.053)	7.590* (±0.105)
Indoxacarb	1	1.300 (±0.053)	5.013* (±0.064)	9.720 (±0.040)	9.607 (±0.076)	9.287 (±0.083)	9.260 (±0.080)	8.493 (±0.050)
	2	1.100 (±0.075)	5.887* (±0.234)	9.490 (±0.187)	9.260 (±0.250)	9.250 (±0.131)	9.073 (±0.101)	8.263 (±0.117)
	4	1.200 (±0.026)	5.820* (±0.178)	9.093* (±0.070)	8.993* (±0.099)	8.763* (±0.075)	8.707* (±0.064)	7.920* (±0.053)

¹Mean ± SD Standard Deviation of three replicates; * Significant level: ($\alpha < 0.05$)

For azoxystrobin, during the first 24 hours of AF, the yeast biomass increased significantly in comparison to control cells. The yeast biomass reached 5.883, 5.980, and 5.487 g.l⁻¹, in the presence of ½MRL, MRL, and 2MRL respectively, which was up to 15% higher than the control group (5.203 g.l⁻¹). This indicates the rapid proliferation of yeast cells under pesticide stress in the fermentation prophase. These findings are consistent with the presence of other strobilurin fungicides, such as kresoxim-methyl and trifloxystrobin, that cause an increase in yeast cell counts

compared to untreated samples at the beginning and during fermentation at concentrations below their EU-MRL (Oliva et al., 2020). It is noteworthy that the final counts of yeast in the presence of azoxystrobin concentrations $\frac{1}{2}$ MRL were higher than the control throughout fermentation. The remarkable higher cell counts in treated wines compared to untreated control samples suggest that this effect may be explained by the chemical constituents of the fortified fungicides as well as the active principle, which contains a variety of other chemicals, including carbon, sulfur, nitrogen compounds, etc., that can be used by yeasts during alcoholic fermentation (Đorđević & Đurović-Peješev, 2016; Oliva et al., 2020). Previous studies showed that soil microorganisms can use azoxystrobin as a sole carbon source (Adetutu, Ball and Osborn, 2008; Feng, 2020). Carboxylic acid metabolite is considered the predominant degradation product formed by the hydrolysis of the E- β -methoxyacrylate MOA-system methyl ester in the strobilurins (azoxystrobin and trifloxystrobin) by microorganisms in soils, water, and other environments (Balba, 2007; Ghosh and Singh, 2009; Singh *et al.*, 2010; Clinton *et al.*, 2011). The growth of *S. cerevisiae* gradually adjusts to the stress created by the fungicide's presence throughout fermentation, as evidenced by the biomass production, which shows behavior similar to the control in the presence of azoxystrobin concentrations equivalent to MRL ($p > 0.05$). However, for concentrations above the MRL, the biomass shows a significant loss ($p < 0.05$) in comparison to the control. The final biomass in the broth containing 2MRL azoxystrobin was 7.6 g.l⁻¹ which was reduced by 10.6% compared to the control. These findings align with the toxic effects of azoxystrobin, which include a reduction in ATP content in *S. cerevisiae* (inhibition of mitochondrial respiration) with increasing concentrations (Adetutu, Ball and Osborn, 2008; Estève *et al.*, 2009), a decrease in dehydrogenase (DHA) activity, and disruption of the energy cycle (Guo *et al.*, 2023), and a reduction in microbial biomass (Adak *et al.*, 2020). Similarly for pyraclostrobin (Gava et al., 2021), strobilurins are normally considered to be stronger inhibitors of spore germination than mycelial growth; hence, their presence in high concentrations results in a significant reduction in biomass amount. Even though the number of cells was significantly affected by the presence of high concentrations of fungicides, a regular fermentative process occurred due to the presence of a sufficient number of yeast cells (Sharma *et al.*, 2005). Similar results were observed during simulated fermentation with 1 mg.l⁻¹ of azoxystrobin, where the individual presence of azoxystrobin showed no inhibitory effect on the fermentation system (Guo *et al.*, 2023).

For indoxacarb, at concentrations equal to or less than the MRL, yeast biomass shows similar behavior as the control throughout fermentation ($p > 0.05$). An identical response to indoxacarb at $\frac{1}{2}$ MRL concentration was observed on *S. cerevisiae* (Zara, Caboni and Orro, 2011). Low concentrations of indoxacarb may be adsorbed to grape must due to its strong lipophilicity with relatively high log K_{ow} of 4.65 causing minimal effect on yeast cells during fermentation (Angioni et al., 2011). However, in the presence of a high concentration of indoxacarb 2MRL in the medium, a marginally significant decrease ($p < 0.05$) when compared to the control, implying that the insecticide has an impact on yeasts through a contact mode of action. The stronger lipophilicity made it easier for indoxacarb to pass through the cell membrane of the yeast cells (Guo *et al.*, 2023). The inhibitory activity of 2MRL of indoxacarb on biomass production was evident once growth assumed the exponential phase. Although there are not enough studies to provide definite evidence that yeast spore germination is reduced during alcoholic fermentation in the presence of indoxacarb, the presence of a chemical component in high concentrations may create stress in yeast cells, which could have an influence on biomass production. It is worth noting that high concentrations of indoxacarb are lethal due to the

blockage of the voltage-gated sodium channel (Zuo *et al.*, 2016), which is found in the plasma membrane of yeast cells (Gustin *et al.*, 1986). Another explanation why indoxacarb's toxicity increased at 2MRL concentrations is that it was decomposed by strain X16 during fermentation, releasing the more lethal N-decarbomethoxylated (DCJW) metabolite that is more effective at inhibiting insect sodium channels (Wang *et al.*, 2020).

3.2. Influence of pesticides on the fermentation kinetics

Figure 3-a,b represent the results of weight loss % (CO₂ release) of *S. cerevisiae* during alcoholic fermentation under the effect of different concentrations of the two pesticides. Yeast cells show normal lag phase in the absence and presence of both the fungicide and the insecticide. Generally, the trend of CO₂ emission percent was the same regardless of the pesticide concentration ($p > 0.05$), indicating that all vinification had a regular course, with identical fermentation rate. The fermentation rate was at its highest during the first two days. Control and treatment groups had completed the alcoholic fermentation within 16 days. The impact of pesticides on the yeast strain fermentative activity was measured by the strain's ability to tolerate these compounds while maintaining its fermentative performance. The fermenting property in the presence of high concentration of pesticides was lower than the control, but after 2 days of rapid fermentation, its accumulated mass loss curve shows no significant difference ($p > 0.05$). As a result, *S. cerevisiae* strain X16 fermentation was not significantly affected by the presence of different concentrations of azoxystrobin and indoxacarb.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. Fermentation behavior of yeast in the absence and presence of different concentration of (a) azoxystrobin and (b) indoxacarb; untreated control, $\frac{1}{2}$ MRL, MRL and 2MRL pesticide enriched.

From the above-mentioned analysis, it was demonstrated that the addition of the MRL concentration and beyond of azoxystrobin show a significant effect on the number of cells with no effect on the viability of cells and overall fermentation process. This is in correlation with earlier established findings, as (Noguerol-Pato *et al.*, 2014) investigated the fermentative kinetics of other strobilurin fungicides (pyraclostrobin and kresoxim-methyl) at concentrations equal to their MRL and found that they had no influence on the kinetics of must fermentation but with slight reduction in yeast biomass concentration. The same conclusion were previously established by (Oliva and Cayuela, 2007), when they proved that none of the two strobilurin fungicides (kresoxim-methyl and trifloxystrobin) produced negative effect on the fermentative kinetics. While it was demonstrated that the addition of high indoxacarb concentrations above MRL into the medium provide a significant negative effect on the growth parameters with no effect on viability and the overall fermentation process. Similar outcomes were attained when high concentrations of indoxacarb was tested against the *Beauveria bassiana* fungus and exhibited toxic effects (Amutha *et al.*, 2010).

3.3. Influence of Azoxystrobin and Indoxacarb on Tartaric Acid production and Reducing Sugar Utilization

The changes in concentrations of total sugar and acids can also reveal the condition of the microorganisms in the fermentation must (Zhao *et al.*, 2020).

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. Reducing sugar (g l⁻¹) (---) and tartaric acid (g l⁻¹) levels during yeast alcoholic fermentation in the absence and presence of different concentration of (a) azoxystrobin and (b) indoxacarb; untreated control, 1/2MRL, MRL and 2MRL pesticide enriched.

Reducing sugar catabolism

Wine yeasts use glucose in their metabolism to synthesize tartaric acid using different metabolic pathways. Over the period of two hours, the sugar levels in our media exceeded the grape juice's starting sugar level (200 g.l⁻¹). This is due to the fact that the yeast degraded sucrose into reducing sugars, increasing the sugar level in each medium (He, 2016). The effect of different fungicide concentration on reducing sugar consumption were shown in **Figure 4**. The difference obtained between different concentrations of fungicide and insecticide-treated samples and control test was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). In all the modalities, yeast was able to easily ferment the synthetic grape juice, since the invertase, the enzyme which decomposes sugar, found in yeast cell wall uses sucrose found in grape juice to initiate fermentation (Navarro *et al.*, 2015). Similarly, (Noguerol-Pato *et al.*, 2014) proved the presence of other strobilurin fungicides, kresoxim-methyl, and pyraclostrobin, did not significantly affect the sugar consumption kinetics of *S. cerevisiae* cells during fermentation. Although azoxystrobin and kresoxim-methyl are structurally similar but (Briz-Cid, Castro-Sobrinho, et al., 2018) proved that the presence of kresoxim-methyl delay fermentation and inhibit sugar catabolism. The physiochemical properties of the fungicide influenced the fermentation and sugar consumption; kresoxim-higher methyl's Log K_{ow} of 3.4 and lower solubility of 2 mg.l⁻¹ increase its toxicity effect.

Tartaric acid production

For both pesticides, concentrations equal to ½MRL show insignificant difference when compared to the control ($p > 0.05$). While the production of tartaric acid in the presence of both pesticides was significantly less than the control during fermentation ($p < 0.05$) at concentrations equal and above MRL **Figure 4**. Similarly, (Ortiz, Peñalver and Navarro, 2010) and (Barba, Oliva and Pay, 2010) proved that presence of azoxystrobin during winemaking process effect the final content of organic acids by lowering tartaric acid concentration.

Despite the differences observed, we can conclude that the pesticide residues do not affect the final quality of wines because the ending levels of tartaric acid range (1.262 - 2.448 g.l⁻¹) were consistent with those of good wine (Cioch-Skoneczny *et al.*, 2021). Since fermentation does not metabolize tartaric acid, its levels are usually stable (Cioch-Skoneczny *et al.*, 2021). While the decrease of tartaric acid at the end of fermentation may be due to the decrease in bitartrate's solubility and the precipitation that occurs as alcohol concentrations increase (Gao *et al.*, 2022).

3.4. Effect of azoxystrobin and indoxacarb on chromatic characteristics of wine

After assessing the effect of azoxystrobin and indoxacarb on yeast growth parameters, we aimed at studying the color intensity and tonality of the produced synthetic wine as a function of different concentrations and yeasts **Table 7**. The chromatic characteristics of the wines were used to characterize them. Measurements at three different wavelengths 420, 520, and 620 nm are used to evaluate the red wines, where A_{420nm}, A_{520nm} and A_{620nm} represent the yellow, red, and blue components of the color intensity.

Table 7. Color intensity (A₄₂₀ + A₅₂₀ + A₆₂₀) and tonality (A₄₂₀/A₅₂₀) of synthetic wine during yeast alcoholic fermentation in the absence and presence of different concentration of azoxystrobin and indoxacarb.

Molecule	Concentration of fortified pesticide (mg kg ⁻¹)	Wine chromatic characteristics (±SD) ¹							
		Time	T ₀	T ₁	T ₂	T ₆	T ₉	T ₁₄	T ₁₆

Control	Color Intensity	6.00 (±0.07)	5.99 (±0.07)	5.88 (±0.15)	5.79 (±0.10)	5.69 (±0.06)	5.67 (±0.06)	5.36 (±0.16)	
	Tonality	0.85 (±0.09)	0.84 (±0.06)	0.71 (±0.06)	0.89 (±0.02)	0.71 (±0.05)	0.73 (±0.07)	0.75 (±0.08)	
Azoxystrobin	Color Intensity	1.5	6.51 (±0.33)	6.58* (±0.06)	6.23* (±0.14)	6.32 (±0.44)	6.25 (±0.34)	6.17 (±0.84)	5.93 (±0.71)
		3	6.65* (±0.16)	6.38* (±0.10)	6.58* (±0.05)	6.48* (±0.09)	6.03 (±0.16)	5.92 (±0.13)	5.89 (±0.28)
		6	6.37 (±0.41)	6.63* (±0.20)	6.63* (±0.05)	6.46* (±0.20)	6.44 (±0.34)	6.20 (±0.20)	6.01 (±0.51)
	Tonality	1.5	0.93 (±0.26)	0.94 (±0.14)	0.90 (±0.04)	0.93 (±0.08)	1.02 (±0.10)	1.01 (±0.20)	1.02 (±0.19)
		3	0.94 (±0.40)	0.94 (±0.31)	0.93 (±0.17)	0.95 (±0.15)	1.00 (±0.02)	0.97 (±0.14)	1.02 (±0.17)
		6	0.94 (±0.29)	0.93 (±0.18)	0.93 (±0.18)	0.95 (±0.15)	0.96 (±0.15)	0.92 (±0.10)	1.03 (±0.24)
Indoxacarb	Color Intensity	1	6.53* (±0.17)	6.85* (±0.11)	6.61* (±0.32)	6.31* (±0.20)	5.96 (±0.06)	5.68 (±0.33)	5.24 (±0.49)
		2	6.15 (±0.25)	6.74* (±0.11)	6.61* (±0.10)	6.32* (±0.24)	5.92 (±0.12)	5.82 (±0.18)	5.46 (±0.46)
		4	6.49 (±0.26)	6.65* (±0.26)	6.38* (±0.10)	6.21* (±0.13)	5.94 (±0.24)	5.66 (±0.36)	5.29 (±0.49)
	Tonality	1	0.81 (±0.13)	0.85 (±0.07)	0.75 (±0.08)	0.86 (±0.02)	0.72 (±0.07)	0.76 (±0.08)	0.76 (±0.05)
		2	0.82 (±0.12)	0.86 (±0.08)	0.78 (±0.07)	0.84 (±0.04)	0.73 (±0.09)	0.74 (±0.11)	0.79 (±0.11)
		4	0.82 (±0.14)	0.87 (±0.09)	0.82 (±0.11)	0.85 (±0.02)	0.76 (±0.09)	0.83 (±0.10)	0.78 (±0.03)

¹ Mean ± SD Standard Deviation of three replicates; * Significant level ($\alpha < 0.05$)

Wine intensity (I) varies widely across different varieties of wine; it is known that it depends on the pigment composition and equilibrium state of the wine's pigments (Somers and Evans, 1974). The synthetic wine showed a significant increase in color intensity for both pesticides within the first six days ($p < 0.05$). (Glories, 1984) study shows that this may be due to increased A_{420} levels along with the yellow component. These modifications may be explained by the increased polymerization rate that these wines present, which decreases the red component and enhances the yellow color (Boido *et al.*, 2006; Monagas *et al.*, 2006). The changes in color intensity is related to yeast strain (Petruzzi *et al.*, 2015), the changes of anthocyanin in wine (He *et al.*, 2012), and the presence of pesticides (Briz-Cid *et al.*, 2014). Considering pesticides and wine polyphenols compete for the same binding sites on the surface of yeast cells during fermentation, it's possible that this pesticide stress on yeast cells during the first six days of fermentation contributed to the difference in color intensity (Caridi *et al.*, 2006). Similar results were found in Monastrell red wines in the presence of 5 MRL of fungicides (iprovalicarb and mepanipyrim) (N Briz-Cid *et al.*, 2018).

Afterwards, from day six until the end of fermentation no significant differences in color intensity between the modalities studied ($p > 0.05$). Although there was no evident change in color intensity at the end of fermentation once

azoxystrobin was prevalent, the I value was higher than 5.7, indicating that the wines were considered to have high intensity color when compared to the control and yet when indoxacarb was present (values lower than 5.7 with light intensity color). The minor increase in the intensity of color of the synthetic wine may be caused by the presence of excess azoxystrobin at the end of fermentation (Skendi, Papageorgiou and Stefanou, 2020).

Wine hue (T) or wine tonality (T) is a measure of wine tint that shows how the color of the wine changes from red to orange as it ages, with young wines displaying values < 1 (0.5-0.7) and aged wines reaching a maximum limit of about 1.2-1.3 (Skendi, Papageorgiou and Stefanou, 2020). The tonality of the resulting wine was less than 1 with no significant difference across the mediums investigated in the presence of both pesticides ($p > 0.05$), as would be predicted given that the fermentation was not affected by the different pesticide concentrations. In winemaking, the control of fermentations, wine stability, and aging processes depends on the adsorption of wine components by yeasts, yeast lees, and inactivated yeast fractions (Petruzzi *et al.*, 2015). Considerable research has examined how yeast cells interact with different wine components, such as anthocyanin, which are mostly responsible for the color of red wines.

3.5. Dissipation kinetics of azoxystrobin and indoxacab during alcoholic fermentation

The dissipation kinetics over a gradient of pesticide concentrations during alcoholic fermentation of *S. cerevisiae* strains were studied at a constant (pH = 3.4 ± 0.3) and temperature (T = 30 ± 1 °C) **Figure 5**. The target pesticide influenced dissipation during alcoholic fermentation. Azoxystrobin and indoxacarb dissipation reactions followed first-order kinetics, since the log-transformed data points produced linear data; the average of these points was used to determine the regression. The experimental data was fitted to a dissipation mathematical model from the equation described in the **Pesticide dissipation decay model** to determine the rate of residue dissipation in each fermentation process **Table 8**.

The dissipation kinetics of azoxystrobin in the fermentation process followed the first-order decay model ($R^2 > 0.93$). The regression equations, half-lives, and rate constants were calculated, and the results are listed in **Table 8**. Between 21.2 and 33% (in mass units) of azoxystrobin residues were eliminated during alcoholic fermentation (16 days). The half-life of azoxystrobin increases as the concentration increases. These observations agree with previous studies, where azoxystrobin slowly decreased with pseudo-first-order kinetics during the vinification process (Cabras *et al.*, 1998). (Wołejko *et al.*, 2016) previously reported that high molecular weight compounds decompose slowly, and the log K_{ow} parameter (the partition coefficient between octanol and water) is important in predicting pesticide adsorption behavior in medium. This explains the slow decomposition of azoxystrobin during alcoholic fermentation **Figure 5-(a)**.

Azoxystrobin's metabolic products and degradation kinetics have not yet been studied. Furthermore, the degradation mechanism of azoxystrobin remains unclear. Azoxystrobin was proven by (Edder *et al.*, 2009) that it doesn't preferentially partition between the liquid and the solid phases, and the quantities found in wines were similar to those on grapes. As indicated by (Cabras *et al.*, 1998), azoxystrobin was preferably adsorbed on organic matter (grape skins). Adsorption of fungicides to grape must reduce its availability for yeast intervention in dissipation during alcoholic fermentation (Adetutu, Ball and Osborn, 2008). Similarly, pyraclostrobin fungicide did not fully dissipate among microbial populations in soil, showing high $t_{1/2}$ values of 28.7 and 47 days. The strobilurin fungicides (azoxystrobin, trifloxystrobin, and kresoxim-methyl) have translaminar movement, allowing them to penetrate the

grape (Adak *et al.*, 2020). Due to this, pesticides can persist during alcoholic fermentation and contaminate the finished product when azoxystrobin levels are high in grapes. This indicated that the centrifugation of samples before analysis allowed the adsorption on grape must and removal of azoxystrobin instead of yeast dissipation. This indicated that, as for azoxystrobin, the residues of trifloxystrobin and pyraclostrobin were adsorbed by the grape lees (Garau *et al.*, 2009).

Table 8. Regression equations, dissipation rates, half-life, and processing factor of different concentrations of azoxystrobin and indoxacarb.

Molecule	Concentration (mg kg ⁻¹)	Regression Equation	Regression Coefficient (R ²)	Rate Constant K _{diss} (Day ⁻¹)	Half-life (Day)	PF ¹ (±SD) ²
Azoxystrobin	1.5	y = - 0.0248x + 0.4261	0.9349	0.025	27.9	0.669 (±0.022)
	3	y = - 0.019x + 1.1185	0.9322	0.019	36.5	0.780 (±0.099)
	6	y = - 0.0138x + 1.7715	0.9765	0.014	50.2	0.789 (±0.018)
Indoxacarb	1	y = - 0.0596x - 0.0594	0.9783	0.060	11.7	0.379 (±0.078)
	2	y = - 0.0746x + 0.6228	0.9824	0.075	9.3	0.302 (±0.030)
	4	y = - 0.0946x + 1.2945	0.9812	0.095	7.3	0.219 (±0.003)

¹ PF: Processing Factor; ² SD: Mean ± SD Standard Deviation of three replicates

The dissipation of indoxacarb followed the first order of kinetics (R² > 0.98). The regression equations, half-lives, and rate constants were calculated, and the results are listed in **Table 8**. The half-life decreased as the concentration of indoxacarb increased, ranging between t_{1/2} = 7.3 and 11.75 days. The dissipation of indoxacarb was highly dependent on the initial spiking concentration **Figure 5-(b)**. The final indoxacarb concentration at the highest indoxacarb concentration, 2MRL, reduced by about 78%, and the mid-range concentration of EU-MRL, which also showed rapid dissipation, decreased by 70%. The amount of indoxacarb decreased by 62% of the starting concentration when it was present at the lowest concentration, ½MRL. During the fermentation process, the insecticide dissipates; the elimination during this phase can be attributed to the yeast's active fermentation. Indoxacarb is considered to have a contact mode of action, which implies that it is more sensitive to stages of processing than systematic pesticides because it is administered to the outside of a crop. The microbial degradation of higher indoxacarb concentrations is currently well studied. Degradation is frequently related to the stimulation of microbial growth and metabolic mineralization, which results in the typical sigmoidal structure of the degradation curves with exponential increases **Figure 5-(b)** and saturation phases (Fomsgaard, 1997). Pesticides must be utilized by organisms

in this degradation process as both an energy and carbon source (Wirsching *et al.*, 2020). It has been demonstrated that degradation rates at higher concentrations cannot always be generalized to lower concentrations (Fomsgaard, 1997). At low pesticide doses, microbial degradation is controlled by fundamentally different preconditions. They reduce the chance of contact by increasing the distance between the molecule and the organism. The distance between the molecules and yeast cells rises at low concentrations of indoxacarb $\frac{1}{2}$ MRL, reducing the probability of contact and decreasing the degradation ability (Wirsching *et al.*, 2020).

The insecticide was distributed between the pomace (solid phase) and fermentation must (liquid phase) during alcoholic fermentation. The log K_{ow} of the octanol-water partition coefficient is an important factor in predicting pesticide adsorption behavior when studying the fate of chemical compounds (Wołejko *et al.*, 2016). The dissipation of indoxacarb may be due to its low water solubility (0.2 mg.l^{-1}), high K_{ow} (hydrophobic), and the fact that it remains undissolved in the liquid phase during alcoholic fermentation (González-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2009). According to the general rule for pesticides, hydrophobic molecules (with a high log K_{ow}) are expelled from the aqueous solution and preferentially accumulate in the solid substrate (Doulia *et al.*, 2016). These molecules tend to concentrate in solid by-products, such as pomace and lees, during the distribution process (Gao *et al.*, 2022), while partitioning more into the microbial phase. The gradual accumulation of chlorinated hydrocarbon insecticides in the food chain is a major source of concern when they are used. The hypothesis is that the uptake of these compounds by live or dead organisms is the first step in this accumulating process (Voerman and Tamme, 1969).

Mannoproteins, the main component of the yeast cell wall, that controls the wall's porosity (Brzobohaty and Kováč, 1986), carry negative charges when they are present in the pH range of wine. As a response, they may form electrostatic and ionic interactions with the other components contained during alcoholic fermentation (Caridi *et al.*, 2006). This structural variability could be the explanation for the wine yeasts' ability to bind to pesticides, which results in their adsorption and removal from contaminated grape musts during alcoholic fermentation. The porosity of the *S. cerevisiae* cell wall, as well as hydrophobic interactions between pesticides and the yeast cell wall, play an important role in pesticide dissipation during fermentation (Morata *et al.*, 2003). Cell surface areas, volume, and cell wall thickness, along with 1,3- β -glucan content, all had an impact on yeast's adsorption abilities (Luo *et al.*, 2015). The β -glucan in the yeast cells at an acidic medium, pH value (pH=3) similar to our alcoholic fermentation pH, has a high affinity for toxin adsorption (Piotrowska and Masek, 2015).

The PFs of two pesticides were calculated during the fermentation process and are shown in **Table 8**. In fermentation, the PFs of different concentrations of azoxystrobin ranged from 0.669 to 0.788, values < 1 . Indoxacarb PFs values ranged between 0.219 to 0.379 less than PFs of azoxystrobin since according to the results, yeast cells were able to significantly dissipate the indoxacarb residual levels in synthetic grape juice during the AF process more than azoxystrobin residues. The findings were consistent with previous observations (Hou *et al.*, 2020), proving that yeast might break down certain pesticides and reduce residues in wine. Several papers investigated the behavior of pesticides from vine to wine as well as the impact of yeast on their residues (Cabras *et al.*, 1995; Angioni *et al.*, 2003; Zara, Caboni and Orro, 2011; Xiao *et al.*, 2020). Fermentation is a crucial step in removing pesticides, particularly lipophilic ones, to enhance wine safety and reduce risks to human health. This effectiveness may be attributed to the complexity of the fermentation system used in the processing experiments. The system features a diverse microbial population, a

variety of reaction types, and dynamic distribution processes between the solid and liquid phases. These factors collectively exert a significant influence on the fate of pesticides during the winemaking process (Gao *et al.*, 2022).

(a) Azoxystrobin

(b) Indoxacarb

Figure 5. Dissipation plot of (a) residual azoxystrobin (b) residual indoxacarb on a linear-log scale using a first order decay mode.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study investigated the ability of the oenological yeast *S. cerevisiae* strain X16 to degrade azoxystrobin and indoxacarb, as well as the effects of various concentrations of these pesticides on yeast cells during alcoholic fermentation. The results demonstrated that yeast cell proliferation tolerates azoxystrobin up to its maximum residue limit (MRL) but is inhibited at twice the MRL concentration of indoxacarb. Additionally, yeast cells produced

less tartaric acid (g.l^{-1}) when exposed to pesticide residues at or above the MRL. Notably, neither pesticide, at different concentrations, had a significant impact on yeast viability, sugar consumption, fermentation profile, or the color intensity of the synthetic wine produced by the end of fermentation. The study revealed that the dissipation of azoxystrobin decreases as its concentration exceeds the recommended application rate, leading to the possibility of high levels persisting in wine throughout fermentation. After alcoholic fermentation, azoxystrobin residues decreased by 33.1% for concentrations below the maximum residue limit (MRL). In contrast, indoxacarb showed more efficient dissipation at concentrations above the MRL compared to those at or below it, with removal rates ranging from 62% to 78% in the final wine. These findings highlight that adhering to good agricultural practices, resulting in pesticide residues at or below the MRL, has an insignificant effect on yeast activity during alcoholic fermentation. Furthermore, the study demonstrated that yeast can dissipate these insecticides during fermentation, offering a basis for future research on the impact of other oxadiazine insecticides on wine quality. While low concentrations of azoxystrobin residues are generally considered safe for consumers under current European and international regulations, higher concentrations pose significant risks to the wine industry, including quality challenges and economic losses. Therefore, careful monitoring and management of pesticide application are essential to ensure both product safety and industry sustainability.

5. References

- Adak, T. *et al.* (2020) 'Target and non-target effect of commonly used fungicides on microbial properties in rhizospheric soil of rice', *International Journal of Environmental Analytical Chemistry*, 100(12), pp. 1350–1361. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03067319.2019.1653457>.
- Adetutu, E.M., Ball, A.S. and Osborn, A.M. (2008) 'Azoxystrobin and soil interactions: degradation and impact on soil bacterial and fungal communities', *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 105(6), pp. 1777–1790. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2672.2008.03948.x>.
- Amutha, M. *et al.* (2010) 'Effect of commonly used insecticides on the growth of white Muscardine fungus, *Beauveria bassiana* under laboratory conditions', (43-146 (2010)), p. 5.
- Angioni, A. *et al.* (2003) 'GC-ITMS Determination and Degradation of Captan during Winemaking', *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 51(23), pp. 6761–6766. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf0342876>.
- Angioni, A. *et al.* (2011a) 'Fate of Iprovalicarb, Indoxacarb, and Boscalid Residues in Grapes and Wine by GC-ITMS Analysis', *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 59(12), pp. 6806–6812. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf2011672>.
- Angioni, A. *et al.* (2011b) 'Fate of Iprovalicarb, Indoxacarb, and Boscalid Residues in Grapes and Wine by GC-ITMS Analysis', *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 59(12), pp. 6806–6812. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf2011672>.
- Balba, H. (2007) 'Review of strobilurin fungicide chemicals', *Journal of Environmental Science and Health, Part B*, 42(4), pp. 441–451. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03601230701316465>.
- Barba, A., Oliva, J. and Pay, P. (2010) 'Influence of Fungicide Residues in Wine Quality', in O. Carisse (ed.) *Fungicides*. InTech. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5772/13174>.

Boido, E. *et al.* (2006) 'Aging Effect on the Pigment Composition and Color of *Vitis vinifera* L. Cv. Tannat Wines. Contribution of the Main Pigment Families to Wine Color', *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 54(18), pp. 6692–6704. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf061240m>.

Bonora, A. and Mares, D. (1982) 'A simple colorimetric method for detecting cell viability in cultures of eukaryotic microorganisms', *Current Microbiology*, 7(4), pp. 217–221. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01568802>.

Briz-Cid, N. *et al.* (2014) 'Effect of Two Anti-Fungal Treatments (Metrafenone and Boscalid Plus Kresoxim-methyl) Applied to Vines on the Color and Phenol Profile of Different Red Wines', *Molecules*, 19(6), pp. 8093–8111. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules19068093>.

Briz-Cid, N. (2018) *Dissipation of Three Fungicides and Their Effects on Anthocyanins and Color of Monastrell Red Wines*. preprint. LIFE SCIENCES. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints201812.0169.v1>.

Briz-Cid, N *et al.* (2018) *Dissipation of Three Fungicides and Their Effects on Anthocyanins and Color of Monastrell Red Wines*. preprint. LIFE SCIENCES. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints201812.0169.v1>.

Briz-Cid, Noelia *et al.* (2018) 'Fungicide residues affect the sensory properties and flavonoid composition of red wine', *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis*, 66, pp. 185–192. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfca.2017.12.021>.

Brzobohaty, B. and KovAC, L. (1986) 'Factors Enhancing Genetic Transformation of Intact Yeast Cells Modify Cell Wall Porosity', *Microbiology*, 132(11), pp. 3089–3093. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1099/00221287-132-11-3089>.

Cabras, P. *et al.* (1995) 'Fate of Some Insecticides from Vine to Wine', *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 43(10), pp. 2613–2615. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf00058a011>.

Cabras, P. *et al.* (1998) 'Fate of Azoxystrobin, Fluazinam, Kresoxim-methyl, Mepanipyrim, and Tetraconazole from Vine to Wine', *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 46(8), pp. 3249–3251. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf980186+>.

Cabras, P. *et al.* (1999) 'Pesticides in Fermentative Processes of Wine', *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 47(9), pp. 3854–3857. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf990005j>.

Cabras, P. and Angioni, A. (2000) 'Pesticide Residues in Grapes, Wine, and Their Processing Products', *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 48(4), pp. 967–973. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf990727a>.

Caridi, A. *et al.* (2006) 'Ochratoxin A removal during winemaking', *Enzyme and Microbial Technology*, 40(1), pp. 122–126. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enzmictec.2006.07.002>.

Cioch-Skoneczny, M. *et al.* (2021) 'The Use of Yeast Mixed Cultures for Deacidification and Improvement of the Composition of Cold Climate Grape Wines', (26), p. 2628. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26092628>.

Clinton, B. *et al.* (2011) 'Bacterial degradation of strobilurin fungicides: a role for a promiscuous methyl esterase activity of the subtilisin proteases?', *Biocatalysis and Biotransformation*, 29(4), pp. 119–129. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3109/10242422.2011.578740>.

Čuš, F. *et al.* (2010) 'Pesticide residues and microbiological quality of bottled wines', *Food Control*, 21(2), pp. 150–154. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2009.04.010>.

De Melo Abreu, S. *et al.* (2005) 'Screening of grapes and wine for azoxystrobin, kresoxim-methyl and trifloxystrobin fungicides by HPLC with diode array detection', *Food Additives and Contaminants*, 22(6), pp. 549–556. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02652030500137918>.

Dorđević, T.M. and Đurović-Pejčev, R.D. (2016) 'The potency of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Lactobacillus plantarum* to dissipate organophosphorus pesticides in wheat during fermentation', *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 53(12), pp. 4205–4215. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13197-016-2408-4>.

Doulia, D.S. *et al.* (2016) 'Removal of pesticides from white and red wines by microfiltration', *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 317, pp. 135–146. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2016.05.054>.

Doulia, D.S. *et al.* (2017) 'Effect of clarification process on the removal of pesticide residues in white wine', *Food Control*, 72, pp. 134–144. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2016.07.035>.

Edder, P. *et al.* (2009) 'Control strategies against grey mould (*Botrytis cinerea* Pers.: Fr) and corresponding fungicide residues in grapes and wines', *Food Additives & Contaminants: Part A*, 26(5), pp. 719–725. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02652030802668578>.

El Dana, F., Hayar, S. and Colosio, M.-C. (2021) 'Selection of Three Indigenous Lebanese Yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* with Physiological Traits from Grape Varieties in Western Semi-Desert and Pedoclimatic Conditions in the Bekaa Valley', 7, p. 280. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/fermentation7040280>.

Estève, K. *et al.* (2009) 'A *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*-based bioassay for assessing pesticide toxicity', *Journal of Industrial Microbiology & Biotechnology*, 36(12), pp. 1529–1534. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10295-009-0649-1>.

European Commission (EC) (2022) *EU Pesticides Database (v.2.2) Pesticide residue(s) and maximum residue levels (mg/kg)*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/pesticides/eu-pesticides-database/mrls/?event=details&pest_res_ids=22,132&product_ids=37,38&v=1&e=search.pr (Accessed: 29 November 2022).

Feng, Y. (2020) 'Kinetics and New Mechanism of Azoxystrobin Biodegradation by an *Ochrobactrum anthropi* Strain SH14'. Edited by W. Zhang *et al.*, (8), p. 625. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms8050625>.

Fomsgaard, I.S. (1997) 'Modelling the mineralization kinetics for low concentrations of pesticides in surface and subsurface soil', *Ecological Modelling*, 102(2–3), pp. 175–208. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3800\(97\)01982-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3800(97)01982-0).

Gajbhiye, V.T. *et al.* (2011) 'Persistence of Azoxystrobin in/on Grapes and Soil in Different Grapes Growing Areas of India', *Bulletin of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology*, 86(1), pp. 90–94. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00128-010-0170-2>.

Gao, J. *et al.* (2022) 'Indigenous *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* Could Better Adapt to the Physicochemical Conditions and Natural Microbial Ecology of Prince Grape Must Compared with Commercial *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* FX10', *Molecules*, 27(20), p. 6892. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules27206892>.

Garau, V.L. *et al.* (2009) 'Residue-free Wines: Fate of Some Quinone outside Inhibitor (QoI) Fungicides in the Winemaking Process', *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 57(6), pp. 2329–2333. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf8029572>.

Gava, A. *et al.* (2021a) 'Occurrence and impact of fungicides residues on fermentation during wine production– A review', *Food Additives & Contaminants: Part A*, 38(6), pp. 943–961. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/19440049.2021.1894357>.

Gava, A. *et al.* (2021b) 'Occurrence and impact of fungicides residues on fermentation during wine production– A review', *Food Additives & Contaminants: Part A*, 38(6), pp. 943–961. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/19440049.2021.1894357>.

Ghosh, R.K. and Singh, N. (2009) 'Effect of Organic Manure on Sorption and Degradation of Azoxystrobin in Soil', *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 57(2), pp. 632–636. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf802716f>.

Glories, Y. (1984) 'La couleur des vins rouges. Ire partie : les équilibres des anthocyanes et des tanins', 18, p. 3. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.20870/oenone.1984.18.3.1751>.

González-Rodríguez, R.M. *et al.* (2009) 'Evolution of tebuconazole residues through the winemaking process of Mencia grapes', *Food Chemistry*, 117(3), pp. 529–537. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2009.04.030>.

Guidance SANTE/12682/2019 (2019) *Guidance Document on Analytical Quality Control and Method Validation Procedures for Pesticides Residues Analysis in Food and Feed*. Available at: <https://www.accredia.it/en/documento/guidance-sante-12682-2019-guidance-document-on-analytical-quality-control-and-method-validation-procedures-for-pesticides-residues-analysis-in-food-and-feed/> (Accessed: 29 November 2022).

Guo, L. *et al.* (2023) 'The interaction effects of pesticides with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and their fate during wine-making process', *Chemosphere*, 328, p. 138577. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2023.138577>.

Gustin, M.C. *et al.* (1986) 'Ion Channels in Yeast', *Science*, 233(4769), pp. 1195–1197. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.2426783>.

Hayek, M. *et al.* (2020) 'The Marine Bacterium *Shewanella woodyi* Produces C8-HSL to Regulate Bioluminescence', *Microbial Ecology*, 79(4), pp. 865–881. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-019-01454-z>.

He, F. *et al.* (2012) 'Anthocyanins and Their Variation in Red Wines II. Anthocyanin Derived Pigments and Their Color Evolution', *Molecules*, 17(2), pp. 1483–1519. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules17021483>.

He, Q. (2016) 'Effect of pesticide residues in grapes on alcoholic fermentation and elimination of chlorothalonil inhibition by chlorothalonil hydrolytic dehalogenase', *Food Control*, p. 7.

Hou, X. *et al.* (2020) 'Rapid analysis and residue evaluation of six fungicides in grape wine-making and drying', *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis*, 89, p. 103465. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfca.2020.103465>.

Jawich, D. *et al.* (2006) 'Effects of penconazole on two yeast strains: Growth kinetics and molecular studies', *Molecular Nutrition & Food Research*, 50(6), pp. 552–556. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/mnfr.200500213>.

Jiang, Y. *et al.* (2009) 'Multiresidue method for the determination of 77 pesticides in wine using QuEChERS sample preparation and gas chromatography with mass spectrometry', *Food Additives & Contaminants: Part A*, 26(6), pp. 859–866. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02652030902822794>.

Jiménez, J.J. *et al.* (2007) 'Persistence and degradation of metalaxyl, lindane, fenvalerate and deltamethrin during the wine making process', *Food Chemistry*, 104(1), pp. 216–223. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2006.11.027>.

Kittelmann, A. *et al.* (2022) 'Transfer of Pesticide Residues from Grapes (*Vitis vinifera*) into Wine—Correlation with Selected Physicochemical Properties of the Active Substances', *Toxics*, 10(5), p. 248. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxics10050248>.

Kosel, J., Raspor, P. and Čadež, N. (2019) 'Maximum residue limit of fungicides inhibits the viability and growth of desirable non-*Saccharomyces* wine yeasts: Maximum residue limit of fungicides inhibits yeasts', *Australian Journal of Grape and Wine Research*, 25(1), pp. 43–52. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/ajgw.12364>.

Luo, Y. *et al.* (2015) 'Effect of Yeast Cell Morphology, Cell Wall Physical Structure and Chemical Composition on Patulin Adsorption', *PLOS ONE*. Edited by E. Dague, 10(8), p. e0136045. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0136045>.

Majed, L., Hayar, S. and Zeitoun, R. (2021) 'The Effects of Formulation on Imidacloprid Dissipation in Grapes and Vine Leaves and on Required Pre-Harvest Intervals under Lebanese Climatic Conditions'. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules27010252>.

Miller, G.L. (1959) 'Use of Dinitrosalicylic Acid Reagent for Determination of Reducing Sugar', *Analytical Chemistry*, 31(3), pp. 426–428. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac60147a030>.

Monagas, M. *et al.* (2006) 'Time course of the colour of young red wines from *Vitis vinifera* L. during ageing in bottle', *International Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 41(8), pp. 892–899. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2621.2005.01132.x>.

Morata, A. *et al.* (2003) 'Adsorption of Anthocyanins by Yeast Cell Walls during the Fermentation of Red Wines', *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 51(14), pp. 4084–4088. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf021134u>.

Mpofu, E. *et al.* (2021) 'Azoxystrobin amine: A novel azoxystrobin degradation product from *Bacillus licheniformis* strain TAB7', *Chemosphere*, 273, p. 129663. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.129663>.

Navarro, S. *et al.* (1999) 'Evolution of Residual Levels of Six Pesticides during Elaboration of Red Wines. Effect of Wine-Making Procedures in Their Dissappearance', *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 47(1), pp. 264–270. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf980801+>.

Navarro, S. *et al.* (2015) 'Behavior of Triazole Fungicide Residues from Barley to Beer', in *Processing and Impact on Active Components in Food*. Elsevier, pp. 525–532. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-404699-3.00063-9>.

Noguerol-Pato, R. *et al.* (2014) 'Influence of new generation fungicides on *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* growth, grape must fermentation and aroma biosynthesis', *Food Chemistry*, 146, pp. 234–241. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2013.09.058>.

Oliva, J. *et al.* (2007) 'Removal of famoxadone, fluquinconazole and trifloxystrobin residues in red wines: Effects of clarification and filtration processes', *Journal of Environmental Science and Health, Part B*, 42(7), pp. 775–781. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03601230701550964>.

Oliva, J. *et al.* (2020a) 'Effect of fungicides on the yeast population during spontaneous fermentation in the vinification of monastrell grapes', *LWT*, 131, p. 109816. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2020.109816>.

Oliva, J. *et al.* (2020b) 'Effect of fungicides on the yeast population during spontaneous fermentation in the vinification of monastrell grapes', *LWT*, 131, p. 109816. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2020.109816>.

Oliva, J. and Cayuela, M. (2007) 'Influence of fungicides on grape yeast content and its evolution in the fermentation', *LWT*, 72(2), pp. 181–189.

Ortiz, J.O., Peñalver, P.P. and Navarro, A.B. (2010) 'Influence of Fungicide Residues in Wine Quality.', p. 21. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5772/13174>.

Oxborough, R.M. *et al.* (2015) 'A new class of insecticide for malaria vector control: evaluation of mosquito nets treated singly with indoxacarb (oxadiazine) or with a pyrethroid mixture against *Anopheles gambiae* and *Culex quinquefasciatus*', *Malaria Journal*, 14(1), p. 353. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-015-0890-1>.

Pan, X. (2018) 'The fate and enantioselective behavior of zoxamide during wine-making process', *Food Chemistry*, p. 7.

Pereira, C. *et al.* (2021) 'Revealing the yeast modulation potential on amino acid composition and volatile profile of Arinto white wines by a combined chromatographic-based approach', *Journal of Chromatography A*, 1641, p. 461991. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2021.461991>.

Petruzzi, L. *et al.* (2015) 'Differential Adsorption of Ochratoxin A and Anthocyanins by Inactivated Yeasts and Yeast Cell Walls during Simulation of Wine Aging', *Toxins*, 7(10), pp. 4350–4365. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins7104350>.

Piotrowska, M. and Masek, A. (2015) 'Saccharomyces Cerevisiae Cell Wall Components as Tools for Ochratoxin A Decontamination', *Toxins*, 7(4), pp. 1151–1162. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins7041151>.

Regueiro, J. *et al.* (2015) 'A Review on the Fermentation of Foods and the Residues of Pesticides—Biotransformation of Pesticides and Effects on Fermentation and Food Quality', *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 55(6), pp. 839–863. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2012.677872>.

Saied, E. *et al.* (2021) 'Evaluate the Toxicity of Pyrethroid Insecticide Cypermethrin before and after Biodegradation by *Lysinibacillus cresolivorans* Strain HIS7', *Plants*, 10(9), p. 1903. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants10091903>.

Sala, C. *et al.* (1996) 'Fate of Some Common Pesticides during Vinification Process', *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 44(11), pp. 3668–3671. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf960218y>.

Salgueiro, S.P., Sá-Correia, I. and Novais, J.M. (1988) 'Ethanol-Induced Leakage in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*: Kinetics and Relationship to Yeast Ethanol Tolerance and Alcohol Fermentation Productivity', *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 54(4), pp. 903–909. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1128/aem.54.4.903-909.1988>.

Sandikly, N., Hayar, S. and Millet, M. (2019) 'Monitoring Survey of Pesticide Residues in Table Grapes and Risk Assessment to Human in Lebanon'. In *Proceedings of the 49ème Congrès du Groupe Français des Pesticides*, Montpellier, France, 21 May. Available at: <http://www.gfpesticides.org/congres/531/532-diaporamas-posters.html>.

Sarris, D. *et al.* (2009) 'Enhanced ethanol production, volatile compound biosynthesis and fungicide removal during growth of a newly isolated *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* strain on enriched pasteurized grape musts', *Engineering in Life Sciences*, 9(1), pp. 29–37. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/elsc.200800059>.

Scariot, F.J. *et al.* (2018) 'Necrotic cell death induced by dithianon on *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*', *Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology*, 149, pp. 137–142. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pestbp.2018.06.006>.

Scariot, F.J., Delamare, A.P.L. and Echeverrigaray, S. (2022) 'The effect of chlorothalonil on *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* under alcoholic fermentation', *Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology*, 182, p. 105032. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pestbp.2021.105032>.

Sharma, J. *et al.* (2005) 'Dissipation of pesticides during bread-making', *Chemical Health & Safety*, 12(1), pp. 17–22. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chs.2004.08.003>.

Sieiro-Sampedro, T. *et al.* (2019) 'Impact of mepanipyrim and tetraconazole in Mencía wines on the biosynthesis of volatile compounds during the winemaking process', *Food Chemistry*, 300, p. 125223. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2019.125223>.

Singh, N. *et al.* (2010) 'Metabolism of ¹⁴C-azoxystrobin in water at different pH', *Journal of Environmental Science and Health, Part B*, 45(2), pp. 123–127. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03601230903471910>.

- Skendi, A., Papageorgiou, M. and Stefanou, S. (2020) 'Preliminary Study of Microelements, Phenolics as well as Antioxidant Activity in Local, Homemade Wines from North-East Greece', *Foods*, 9(11), p. 1607. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods9111607>.
- Somers, T.C. and Evans, M.E. (1974) 'Wine quality: Correlations with colour density and anthocyanin equilibria in a group of young red wines', *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 25(11), pp. 1369–1379. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.2740251105>.
- Song, B. *et al.* (2022) 'Effects of Different Pesticides on the Brewing of Wine Investigated by GC-MS-Based Metabolomics', *Metabolites*, 12(6), p. 485. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/metabo12060485>.
- Sun, X. *et al.* (2019) 'Effect of high Cu²⁺ stress on fermentation performance and copper biosorption of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* during wine fermentation', *Food Science and Technology*, 39(1), pp. 19–26. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1678-457x.24217>.
- Terpou, A. *et al.* (2019) 'Effect of Myclobutanil Pesticide on the Physiological Behavior of Two Newly Isolated *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* Strains during Very-High-Gravity Alcoholic Fermentation', *Microorganisms*, 7(12), p. 666. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms7120666>.
- Voerman, S. and Tammes, P.M.L. (1969) 'Adsorption and desorption of lindane and dieldrin by yeast', *Bulletin of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology*, 4(5), pp. 271–277. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01560911>.
- Wang, Qinqin *et al.* (2020) 'Mechanisms of Increased Indoxacarb Toxicity in Methoxyfenozide-Resistant Cotton Bollworm *Helicoverpa armigera* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)', *Toxics*, 8(3), p. 71. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxics8030071>.
- Wirsching, J. *et al.* (2020) 'Biodegradation of Pesticides at the Limit: Kinetics and Microbial Substrate Use at Low Concentrations', *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 11, p. 2107. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.02107>.
- Wołejko, E. *et al.* (2016) 'The influence of effective microorganisms (EM) and yeast on the degradation of strobilurins and carboxamides in leafy vegetables monitored by LC-MS/MS and health risk assessment', *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 188(1), p. 64. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-015-5022-4>.
- Xiao, O. *et al.* (2020) 'Influence of Triazole Pesticides on Wine Flavor and Quality Based on Multidimensional Analysis Technology', *Molecules*, 25(23), p. 5596. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25235596>.
- Zara, S., Caboni, P. and Orro, D. (2011) 'Influence of fenamidone, indoxacarb, pyraclostrobin, and deltamethrin on the population of natural yeast microflora during winemaking of two sardinian grape cultivars', 46, pp. 491–497. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03601234.2011.583869>.
- Zhang, J. *et al.* (2018) 'Disruption of the cell wall integrity gene ECM33 results in improved fermentation by wine yeast', *Metabolic Engineering*, 45, pp. 255–264. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymben.2017.12.012>.
- Zhao, C. *et al.* (2020) 'Correlations between microbiota with physicochemical properties and volatile flavor components in black glutinous rice wine fermentation', *Food Research International*, 138, p. 109800. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2020.109800>.
- Zhong, W. *et al.* (2020) 'Isolation and Selection of Non-*Saccharomyces* Yeasts Being Capable of Degrading Citric acid and Evaluation Its Effect on Kiwifruit Wine Fermentation', *Fermentation*, 6(1), p. 25. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/fermentation6010025>.
- Zuo, Y. *et al.* (2016) 'Sublethal Effects of Indoxacarb and Beta-Cypermethrin on *Rhopalosiphum padi* (Hemiptera: Aphididae) Under Laboratory Conditions', *Florida Entomologist*, 99(3), pp. 445–450. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1653/024.099.0316>.

Preprint

Preprint

Preprint

Preprint

Preprint

Preprint

Preprint

Preprint

Preprint